

AN INVESTIGATION ON BEARING FATIGUE OF INTERFERENCE-FIT BOLTED COMPOSITE JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

An experimental investigation was conducted to determine the effect of several influencing factors on the fatigue behavior of interference-fit bolted composite joints. The types of bolts, the sizes of interference fit, different materials of laps, and stacking sequences of main laminates were separately considered. Tension-compression reversed force/stress ratio, $R=-1$, was selected to evaluate the fatigue tests. The appropriate levels of fatigue stress were determined by the ultimate bearing strength of the fastener structure obtained from the static tensile tests. The bearing stress and the fatigue life (S-N) data of all specimens were presented and the relationship between influencing factors and fatigue life were obtained. The experimental results showed that the appropriate size of interference fit, the right type of fasteners, and the matched laps could improve the fatigue life of composite joints; however stacking sequences of main laminates was not sensitive to the fatigue life of composite joints.

1 INTRODUCTION

At present, the research on the fatigue properties of high-performance composites has been very broad and extensive. As the composite materials has become more and more widely used in the fields of aerospace, aviation and automotive, the fatigue performance of the whole plane and the fatigue life of composite structure have also attracted more and more attention. In the design of composite structure, researchers have not only satisfied with the fatigue analysis of the composite material itself, but also need to pull enough energy in the fatigue performance research of composite structure. A series of problems will be faced in the design of composite structure withstanding fatigue load, such as selecting the appropriate connection material and method according to the required fatigue performance, assessment of structural fatigue damage, the design of safe fatigue life to ensure the reliability of the connection and so on.

When co-curing technology is widely applied in composite structures, it can greatly reduce the assembly processes of aircraft manufacturing industry, however the mechanical joint is still the key method of connecting high performance composites into effective structures [1]. Extrusion fatigue performance of mechanical joint is generally affected by the selection of R-ratio, fastener type, fastener preload/torque, fastener bolt-hole clearance, and environmental conditions. Chen [2] investigated the extrusion performance and the bolt torque / preload relaxation of bolted joints under hygrothermal environment. The results showed that preload improved the failure strength and the fatigue life of specimen at room temperature. The effects of loading frequency, stress ratio R value, and thermal aging were studied by fatigue test [3]. When the frequency of experimental loading changed from 0.1 Hz to 10 Hz or subjected to a thermal aging time of 10,000 hours, the connection structure was almost non-sensitive to its fatigue life. Under the cyclic stress, the bolts had serious structural fatigue failure due to the change of structural rigidity and damping [4]. Starikov et al. [5] studied the fatigue response of composite joints with countersunk titanium alloy fasteners and composite fasteners, and obtained the same conclusion as in the literature [6]. Ibrahim and Pettit [7] reviewed the role of joints parameter uncertainties and relaxation on the design and dynamic behavior of metallic and composite structure.

With the development of advanced technologies and manufacturing processes, the interference-fit joints are attempting to be used in composite structures for getting a better fatigue performance. There are scatter studies about the effect of interference-fit pin installation, stress distribution, static strength analysis on composite interference-fit bolted or pinned joints in the literature [8-12]. However, there

are few studies about the effect of interference fit on the fatigue behavior of double-lap single bolted composite joints. Therefore, in this paper the experimental investigations are conducted in order to study the fatigue properties of interference-fit bolted composite joints, with considering the factors of the types of bolts, the sizes of interference fit, different materials of laps, and stacking sequences of main laminates.

2 EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The research on the fatigue problem of composite joints has been based on the experiment as the main method. Although there are many achievements in the research on the mechanism of fatigue damage and the simulation method has also made great progress, the experimental investigation is still the only way to verify the analysis results and the basis study of structural fatigue. The fatigue properties of composite joints are not only affected by the fatigue properties of the material itself, but also by many other factors. The influence of these factors on the fatigue properties of composite joints can not be described by the exact mathematical relation, and the fatigue properties of the structures can not be deduced by the fatigue performance of the material. It is necessary to combine the fatigue properties of the material and the data of bearing fatigue tests, in order to finally get the bearing fatigue characteristics of composite joints.

The same composite laminates (T700/BP9916) were selected for the tests of different composite joints. The geometric size of laminate is with of 90×25mm and 5mm diameter fastener hole. All joints were made with the same $w/d = 5$ ratio, $e/d = 3$ ratio, and specimen length of 210mm. A double lap joint, with two lap laminates transferring load to a main laminate, was used in all tests, since this could provide the most stable configuration and minimize the effect of bending in compression. Taking into the account of the length of specimen, a metal fixture was used to avoid the bending of specimen in compression.

Applied cyclic stress level of fatigue tests is obtained from the static bearing strength, in order to get a reasonable S-N curve. Static and fatigue bearing tests were performed by using an INSTRON 8801 dynamic test machine. Static tests were conducted under room condition with 1mm/min ramp speed. For the fatigue tests, the type of cyclic load applied to all specimens was a constant amplitude sine wave with a tension-compression reversed stress ratio $R=-1$. During static and fatigue tests, the deformation of the bearing hole was measured by extensometer. Joint damage can be indicated through joint stiffness reduction or hole elongation (wear around the hole). Testing was not generally terminated until enough bolt-hole elongation was produced (it may be 4% deformation of hole diameter) or 10^6 cycles were achieved.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Different type of fasteners

In order to compare the effect of different types of fasteners on the fatigue life of the structure, Figure 1 showed the S-N curves of the experimental results of the two fastened configurations (blind bolt fastener and high lock bolt fastener) under semi-logarithmic coordinates. As seen from the fitting S-N curves, the fatigue life of blind bolt was about 10 times higher than that of high lock bolt at the same cyclic stress level. When the cyclic stress level was $\pm 50\% \sigma^{bru}$ ($\pm 600\text{MPa}$, σ^{bru} is the ultimate static bearing strength 1,200MPa), the average fatigue life of the blind bolted structures was more than 100,000 times, while the fatigue life of the high-lock bolted joints was only 1,000 times, two orders of magnitude less than blind bolted joints.

Figure 1: The S-N curves of blind bolt and high lock bolt fasteners.

Due to the fact that there was actually a slight amount of clearance between the bolt and hole during the process of connecting assembly, the fasteners under the action of the tension and compression load were continuously impacted on the wall at the beginning of the fatigue test, resulting in the cumulative impact damage around the hole of the composite laminates, and speeding up the failure of the composite structure. On the one hand, after the preparation of the test piece, the fastener was brought into close contact with the load hole, that is, the initial actual nail gap is zero. Only after some fatigue cycles, the hole of composite material could be damaged and produce deformation. Then the gap of bolt and hole generated and increased until the appearance of the impact damage, which was relative to the high lock bolt with H9/h9 tolerance. Blind bolt with 0% interference largely delayed the impact damage under cyclic loading. On the other hand, the tiny burr layer of the laminates was compressed to form a layer of micro burr elastic layer after the assembly of 0% interference fit so that the stress around the hole was redistributed and the stress concentration coefficient would be reduced to a certain extent. For the above two aspects, the blind bolt with 0% interference fit could improve the fatigue life of the composite joints rather than the high lock bolt with sliding.

3.2 The sizes of interference fit

The blind bolted joints of four interference fit sizes (0% neat fit, 0.5%, 1.8%, 3%) were tested separately. The bearing stress and the fatigue life (S-N) data of different interference fit sizes specimen were presented and the relationship between interference fit sizes and fatigue life were obtained (in Fig.2). The best size of interference fit of bolted joints was influenced by the cyclic stress levels. At different dynamic stress levels, the best interference fit of the bolted joints was not always invariable. For the material T700/BP9916 studied in this paper, the fatigue life of the joints with 3% interference fit was the longest in lower bearing stress (less than ± 540 MPa), however in higher bearing stress (more than ± 660 MPa), the joints of the longest fatigue life was with 1.8% interference fit.

Figure 2: The S-N curves of four sizes of interference fit bolted joints.

The Power function formula is usually used as one important mathematical formula of S-N Curves to describe the fatigue characteristics of composite structures.

$$S/\sigma^{bru} = b - m \log N \tag{1}$$

It can be seen from Fig.2 that the relationship between the size of interference fit (I) and the material performance parameters (d and m) was not a simple linear, and presented a complex high-order relationship. In this paper, the relationship between the size of interference fit and its numerical relationship (see Fig.3) and the corresponding quadratic curves (equation 2 and 3) were obtained by the fitting of the material performance parameters.

Figure 3: The fitting curves of the material performance parameters (d and m).

$$d = 1165 + 1074I - 323.6I^2 \tag{2}$$

$$m = 113.3 + 191.7I - 58.96I^2 \quad (3)$$

Equation 2 and 3 are brought into Equation 1 to obtain the relationship between the size of interference fit and the fatigue performance, and finally the S-N relationship under different sizes of interference fit was induced.

$$S = (1165 + 1074I - 323.6I^2) - (113.3 + 191.7I - 58.96I^2) \lg N \quad (2)$$

Since each group of samples were more than 10 and the confidence degree was 95% in the fatigue test, the test data was so reliable that the law under the SN relationship derived from the test data could be fully applicable to other size of interference fit, which could be used as a reference for the design and analysis of the composite joints with interference fit.

3.3 Different materials of laps

In order to compare the effect of different overlapping plates on the compression fatigue properties of the composite structure, three types of laps (aluminum, steel, and composite) in interference fit bolted joints were investigated in fatigue tests. The loading waveform of dynamic stress was sine wave, the maximum cyclic stress amplitude was $\pm 667\text{MPa}$ ($\pm 55\%\sigma^{brn}$) and the frequency of cyclic load was 5HZ.

Figure 4: Comparison of three laps of interference fit bolted joints.

As seen in Fig.4, the fatigue life of the aluminum-lap joint increased with the increase of the interference amount from 0% to 1.8%, and declined with the increase of the interference amount from 1.8% to 3%. For the steel-lap joint, the fatigue life continued to increase with the interference increasing from 0% to 3%. It could be concluded that the fatigue life of three kinds of overlapped joints increased with the increase of the interference amount from 0% to 1.8%. When the interference amount was 3%, the fatigue life of the steel overlap joint was the largest, the aluminum overlap joint was the second, and the composite overlap joint was the lowest.

3.4 Stacking sequences of main laminates

The fatigue tests were carried out on the four lay-ups (table 1) of main plates in composite bolted joints. The loading waveform of dynamic stress was sine wave, the maximum cyclic stress amplitude was $\pm 667\text{MPa}$ ($\pm 55\%\sigma^{brn}$), and the frequency of cyclic load was 2HZ.

Specimen number	Stacking sequence
P6	[45/0/-45/90/0/0/45/0/-45/0] _s
P7	[45/0/-45/0/45/90/0/-45/0/45\ -45] _s
P8	[45/0/-45/0/45/90/-45/0/45/-45] _s
P9	[45/-45/90/45/-45/45/-45/0/45\ -45] _s

Table 1: Stacking sequences of main plates for specimen groups.

Figure 5: Effect of stacking sequences of main plates on the fatigue life of joints.

Fig.5 compared the results of fatigue tests on four different lay-up structures of P6, P7, P8 and P9. The fatigue life of the main plate P6 was the longest, the fatigue life of the main plate P7 was short, and the fatigue lives of the main plates P8 and P9 were basically the same. Therefore, it could be concluded that the fatigue lives of four different layers were close to each other. On the condition of 1.8% interference fit, the influence of different stacking sequence on the connection fatigue life was insignificant.

4 CONCLUSIONS

An experimental study had been carried out to investigate the effect of several factors (the types of bolts, the sizes of interference fit, different materials of laps, and stacking sequences of main laminates) on the fatigue behavior of bolted joints in composite laminates. The static ultimate bearing strengths of neat fit and interference fit were obtained through static tensile tests. The relationship between S-N curves and failure mechanism were examined. Thus, the following results are concluded:

- (1) The fatigue performance of the blind bolted joint was better than that of the high-locking bolted joint. The fatigue life of the blind bolted joints was 1-2 orders of magnitude higher than that of the high-locking bolted joint under the same cyclic stress, and the limit fatigue strength of the blind bolted joints was over 50MPa higher than that of the high-locking bolted.
- (2) The size of interference fit had a great influence on the fatigue life of composite bolted joints. The fatigue life of the best interference and the worst interference (0%, neat fit) would be a difference of 5 to 10 times from the S-N curves.
- (3) Different materials of laps also had a small effect on the fatigue life of composite bolted joints. When the size of interference fit increased from 0% to 3%, the fatigue life of aluminum laps increased first and then decreased, and the fatigue life of steel laps increased gradually. The

fatigue life of the metal laps was slightly higher than that of the composite laps.

- (4) Under the condition that the cyclic stress was $\pm 55\% \sigma^{bru}$ and the size of interference fit was 1.8%, stacking sequences of main laminates had no obvious effect on the fatigue life of the nailing interference joint structure.

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